

Gesture and Emotional Design in Multimodal Human-Computer Interaction using Semiotic Analysis.

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Abstract: The design of gesture-based interactive systems, where an emotional response may be potentially evoked, is a substantial and enduring challenge for designers of interactive systems. The discussion to follow looks at the use of semiotics to analyse expressive gesture generation in theatre, yoga, and multimodal human-computer interaction to establish design foundations, these being interpretable, ephemeral, and programmable elements. A description of an interactive gestural film game *To be or not to be* is included as an appendix showing the application of the elements.

See <http://www.Betaspace.Net.Au/Content/View/36/>

Keywords: *Emotion, gesture, metaphor, metonymy, enunciation.*

1.0 The Problem

Designing interactive gestural systems has been consistently met with complexity and obstacles; data could easily be obtained for gestural movement but the way in which to structure an interaction proved to be challenging [1] the complex flow of movement proving to be elusive [2]. *Put that there* by Bolt [3] was the first instance of coordinated voice and deictic (pointing commands practically demonstrated in an interface, on screen virtual objects from this sensory combination. The expectation that arises from such work was that human gestures that may communicate expressiveness and emotional intention might also be usefully integrated into an interface experience. Pantic [4] described the project as ‘machine context sensing’, and emphasised that progress had been made but that the analysis of affect remained a challenge, whilst Jaimes and Sebe [5] described the processes and multimedia fusion – or the integration of gesture and emotion as ‘still in their infancy’ in what is known as multimodal human computer interaction (MMHCI) where a ‘modality’ is a single sensory input / output.

From an artistic perspective where artists use technology to develop an interaction, the early experiments with such work were evident in the work by the Cage / Cunningham [6] experiments where music and choreography were integrated in to make artworks using video and sensing technology. However, in survey by Cadoz and Wanderley [7] of gesture definitions used by artists and researchers, no single clear principle emerged even though the notion of a language or a grammar of gestures that might lead to a clear body language seemed possible or logical. The question that gesture and emotional response could progress would have to respond to some fundamental questions. These are:

- what categories of human sensory perception should be included, especially considering the increasing range of sensory input devices?
- what arrangement of devices will work, offering coherent and engaging usability?

2.0 Semiotic Analysis: Designing a Matrix of Gesture, Emotion and Technology.

The approach employed in making *To be or not to be* was to apply semiotic analysis to both the human gestures and to the input and output processes present in multimodal human computer interaction, thus creating parity of the gestural elements with the technological elements. The human gestural elements were located in two gesture processes, yoga [8], the ancient Hindu exercise and text based theatrical performance [9], both having long standing definitive and repeatable processes. The technological input and output were similarly subjected to analysis, the result being a design matrix indicating what aspects of gestural processes could be programmed, other elements proving to interpretable in the same way that words have interpretable semantic dimensions, and leaving also ephemeral or undefined experiences.

3.0 Semiotic Definitions: Metaphor, Metonymy, Enunciation.

The key semiotic tools used are Jakobson's [10] notions of *metonymy* and *metaphor*, to which is also added the term, *enunciation* (see Table 1); the first two terms are characteristic of Jakobson's work on semiotics, metaphors being that which represents something else or other – from the Greek *metapherein* meaning 'to transfer' [11], whilst metonymies represent the same – also from the Greek meaning 'to change name'. The third term, *enunciation* indicates the presence of the speech act, bringing attention to the temporality of the communication system under examination. These terms and their temporal characteristics are represented in Table 2.

Table 1. Key Semiotic Terms and their Definitions

Semiotic Terms	Definition
Metaphor	Representation of other
Metonymy	Representation of same
Enunciation	Ephemeral, not unlike speech

Further distinction which bears agreeable comparison is that ‘a metaphor is a way in which one entity is viewed as another’ whilst a metonymy is ‘one entity standing for another’ [12]. Metaphor, then, is a change of form, where one thing represents another; metonymy is different in that the only the name changes and not the form. The typical example of metonymies is when a word substitutes an entity, for example when we speak of the ‘crown’ as representing a kingdom. The key principle to metonymic structures as they are used here is they are chain-like or sequential, allowing for the name change to occur. Metaphors on the other hand do not readily interchange as the equivalence of one form standing in place of another bestows a unique quality on the nature of the metaphor created.

Table 2. Temporal aspects of the key semiotic terms

Semiotic Term	Temporal quality
metaphor	instantaneous
metonymy	sequential
enunciation	enduring

4.0 Abstraction of Semiotic Terms

The key terms *metaphor*, *metonymy* and *enunciation* (see Table 3) will be abstracted, emphasising their key characteristics. In this way, *metaphors* are characterised by *form* in that a representation or symbol of the other must be generated for a metaphor to occur; metonymies, where that which is stands for itself, are *sequential*, in that meaning is derived through the matter assembly of present elements. Finally, *enunciation* is described as a *wave*, in that it resembles the ephemeral nature of wave form energy. A fourth category is included, *world*, referring to the realm of the term used. Semiotic terms are *mental constructions* describing the idea of language, and are therefore of the realm of the mind.

Table 3. Abstraction of Semiotic Terms

Abstraction	Semiotic Terms
Form	Metaphor
Sequence	Metonymy
Wave	Enunciation
World	Mind

5.0 Semiotic Analysis of Yoga: a Gestural System

Yoga, an ancient Hindu exercise used to develop and strengthen body, mind and spirit, is often used by the performing artists to train their body ready for the diverse forms of expression that may be called upon in performance. In the theatrical performance training developed by the director Grotowski [13] for a theatre style known as *Poor Theatre*, particular attention was given to the actor being aware of the body so as to have expressive control of the corpus. Yoga movements such as shoulder stands, back arches and twists, were to be practised to gain expressive control of gestures in performance.

Actors manufacture gesture because they are required to produce a similar controlled performance time and time again. As Saussure states that [14] to ‘bow down before the Emperor nine times’ is a codified gesture of obedience; the same is true for performing gestural artist who is trained to perform a sequence of gestures, usually with an expressive purpose.

Yoga then, must possess fundamental processes for evolving gestural expression. The virtuoso violinist Yehudi Menuhin, a dedicated practitioner of yoga, stated that the body is the ‘first instrument’ and that yoga taught one how ‘to play it’ [15]. The technique is to practise a strict routine of posed forms - known as *asanas* – developing the introspection of feeling that accompanies these gestures. Choreographers also often employ yoga to exercise the group, the sequence of gestures acting as a grammar of body language to prepare for expression, bearing strong procedural similarities to the formal classical techniques of bar exercises [16].

What constitutes yoga is the formation of bodily poses in a predetermined sequential pattern as established in the tradition of a practice. For example, when one starts a yoga class, squatting on the knees is often employed because it most rapidly challenges breathing patterns that have

occurred as a result of responding to the normal outside world. Through this, the aim is to develop a serene, inwardly focused attitude with a departure from external, worldly concerns to focus on what one is experiencing in the body. Yoga asanas emphasize the range of gestures that can be created by the body (see Figure 1a, 1b, 1c, 1d).

Figure 1a

Figure 1b

Figure 1c

Figure 1d

Figures 1a, 1b, 1c, 1d, four yoga poses. Pose 3a and pose 3b would occur early in the sequence as they are known as standing poses, exercising the larger, prone muscle groups in the body. Pose 3c would occur later, developing balance; 3d is designed to twist and release the spine. The images show the range of gesture movement in the human body. A dynamic range is desirable for actors as it increases the potential for expressive range. (Images compliments of Nicole Walsh)

A typical class will follow the instructions of a teacher, for example, being told to ‘stand straight, place your feet firmly on the floor, pay attention to your toes and how they spread out. Feel the arches of your feet and how they lift from the floor...’ and so on. This kind of progressive description instructs the *action* to be taken, allowing the participant to re-experience the body consciously. There may be a variety of responses: we may feel numb, stiff or energised in a particular limb or part of the body. The emphasis is on experiencing the body as it is, without a

sense of urgency or judgement. The practitioner comes to know without knowing they know it; this is critical for raising intuitive awareness [17]. *Being* is what matters; a state of acceptance. Yoga in Sanskrit means *to bind*: that which is separate in us, is brought into one. The practitioner is brought into the *now*. In Yoga the purpose is to integrate the senses as an individual experience into singular focus into the present moment, hence, its usefulness in training for theatrical performance where all actions and dialogue occur in the moment of performance.

Each gesture in yoga has a name, describing the qualities of the form, indicating the critical role in gestural formation that gestures and their accompanying emotions possess. The individual forms represent and embody the experience of the stated emotions in the gesture. The Child's Pose (Hindu name 'virassana') is gentle and submissive, crouching down on the floor with the forehead resting on the mat. The Warrior Pose (Hindu name 'virabhadrasana') is strong; the legs half squatting, the arms raised horizontally. The goal is to attain the execution of each form as fully as possible, with increasing attention to details such as stance, alignment of limbs and bone structures, and ease of execution.

The procession of movements encourage stretching, strengthening, then relaxing the body, its muscles and nerves, stimulating the organs of the body and developing gestural control. These characteristics vary from style to style of yoga practice but they all share the same purpose of raising awareness of bodily states, that is, awareness of how one feels by bringing active attention to the various parts of the body. The expressivity of a part of the body is engaged through the pose, each pose exercising the body in energetically different ways. Feelings are thus heightened and the body is brought into the now, a very useful quality for the performing artist who performs in the moment.

There is little improvisation in yoga; the forms and routines are generally strict. The purpose of the activity is to engage in discipline; at the same time one may soften into the discipline, as one of the key challenges is flexibility and sensitivity. By creating a rigid outer form, a freedom is found within and through the form created by becoming conscious of the feelings occurring during the execution of the pose. Individuality is encouraged but only as a choice of forms and routines for the advanced student. Feelings, then are the domain into which yoga encourages exploration; they are variable within a set paradigm of gestural activity. It is for this reason that performing artists such as actors and dancers find the discipline useful as it exercises the expressive capacity of the body.

Returning again to the semiotic tools of *metaphor*, *metonymy* and *enunciation* (see Table 10), the following equivalences can be made of yoga:

The *metaphoric* aspect of yoga is pose formation or the asana. These forms are still, image-like and, in being given names that describe the likeness of an image or a quality, establish the pose as a metaphor, standing for something other than what it is.

The *metonymic* aspect of yoga is its sequence of forms, the form following strict patterns for the exercise to be useful to the participant. The procession of forms creates a narrative structure which broadly interpreted is the cycle from birth to death to rebirth through an energetically rejuvenated body; the final pose of a yoga session is called 'sivassana' which translated means 'corpse pose', the death, presaging the birth of new consciousness in the participant. In this way the participant has played out a mini-drama of sequenced gestures to the pre-established script of forms.

The *enunciation* and its equivalent in yoga is the most difficult to recognise in that this quality is the most abstract. Recognising the enunciation as the vocalised present, existing in the moment, this quality is forever present and is a consistent goal of yoga trying to bring the body out of distracted thoughts into the experience of *feeling*. This pushes aside the memory and egotistical desires or fears that we may hold at any particular time. The goal is 'acceptance' and to experience 'what is' in the present through the body. This is like a performance in that it is ephemeral and acted out in real time, each experience of the exercise unique, just as every moment in time is unique.

Yoga makes structures of gestures through giving feelings a gestural form; the feelings are discovered; the forms are given and occur in a sequence of conscious comparison. Specifically, it employs *metaphors* of meaning which characterise the movement which are the separate poses; secondly it is *metonymic* in that a sequence of gestures forms the expression of the movement; and thirdly, it has the quality of *enunciation* in that it is concerned with the expressive 'now' of feelings. These elements and equivalences are represented in Table 4.

Table 4 Semiotic analysis of gesture / pose formation in yoga.

Abstraction	Semiotic Term	Semiotic analysis of Yoga
Form	Metaphor	Gesture (pose)
Sequence	Metonymy	Narrative
Wave	Enunciation	Emotion
World	Mind	Somatic

6.0 Semiotic Analysis of Expressive Gesture Generation in Theatre

It is first necessary to describe the model of theatrical process of *text*, *rehearsal* and *performance* (see Figure 2). This is based on Stanislavski's [18] theatrical process where text is used primarily as a blueprint to evolve expressive gesture and dialogue for performance. Directors read the text interpreting the world that will be created then actors rehearse the gestural positions required to deliver dialogue which is then finally remembered as a fixed work for performance.

Figure 2. Model of Stanislavskian theatrical process.

From this a number of distinctions can be made using semiotic analysis:

Thought is required, a cognitive construct, to read the script as a sequence of mental images to be translated into a combination of gestural action and dialogue; secondly, *gesture*, accompanied by dialogue, is the actions of characters, and such action gets the narrative plot from the beginning, to the middle and through to the end; thirdly, *emotion* is inscribed in the text and evolves with interpretation of the character and emerges from text. It is the nature of the dialogue, of the scenario built, allowing the process of emotional interpretation to occur. Forms of representation may change, meaning that the emotional tenor of a work is, in fact, arbitrary.

From the application of semiotic tools to the above terms it can be established that: *gestures* bear equivalence to *metaphors* in that a single gestural form representing an emotional state is represented; *thought* as expressed in language is *metonymic* in nature in that a sequence of words is used; *emotion* bears resemblance to *enunciation* in that enunciation is ephemeral and passing, as are emotions. The semiotic equivalence of dramatic aspects of gestural creation in theatre is represented in Table 5.

Table 5. Semiotic analysis of text-based narrative theatre processes

Abstraction	Semiotic Term	Dramatic Aspect
Form	Metaphor	Gesture
Sequence	Metonymy	Thought (language)
Wave	Enunciation	Emotion
World	Mind	Stage

7.0 Semiotic Analysis of MMHCI

The following definition of MMHCI inputs / outputs establishes the elements of the analysis:

.....perception via one of the *three perception channels*. You can distinguish the three modalities: visual, auditive and tactile (physiology of senses)

(Charwat, 1992) [19]

If we apply semiotic analysis to these input / output attributes of sound, image and touch we can make the following equivalences:

Firstly, *image* is equivalent to *metaphor* in that the image in a computer interface stands for something else: it is representational. It is the image quality of the interface that allows gestural interaction; secondly, *touch* is a *metonymy*, a linear, coded interpretable graduated unit standing for nothing but itself; thirdly, *sound* is equivalent to *enunciation*, the sonic, which is purely vibrational and has no seen or symbolic representations. These equivalences are represented in Table 6 as:

Table 6. Semiotic analysis of modalities in HCI

Abstraction	Semiotic Term	MMHCI input /output
Form	Metaphor	Image / Sound
Sequence	Metonymy	Touch
Wave	Enunciation	Emotion
World	Mind	Electronic

8.0 Semiotic Matrix of Gesture, MMHCI and Related Elements

Using the theatrical model and adding to it the dimension of emotion, establishes its potential use and purposes and how it may be used in Artistic HCI design. The matrix shows that distinct differences and correlations occur. The matrix classifies elements that are as metaphorical, interpreted generally as a *form*. Metaphorical elements are non-programmable but rather require individual, contextually based interpretation, not unlike interpreting how one feels about a colour, a piece of music, or a person. Enunciation is the assigned quality of any ephemeral or time-based process that cannot be captured or defined, rather it simply happens and is described as a *wave meaning that they are neither interpretable* (emotions are what they are) *or programmable*; metonymic elements are elements that are systematic in nature, exhibiting a sequential regularity and are therefore programmable. These relationships are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Semiotic matrix of human and computer elements: MMHCI, yoga and theatrical model.

Abstraction	Semiotic	MMHCI	Yoga	Theatrical Model
Form	Metaphor	Image / sound	Gesture	Gesture
Wave	Enunciation	Emotion	Emotion	Emotion
Sequence	Metonymy	Touch	Narrative	Text
World	Linguistic	Virtual	Somatic	Stage

9.0 Semiotic Matrix: Interpretable, Programmable and Ephemeral Elements

Table 8 shows these relationships further simplified as to the essential requirements for the design. Significantly, it shows the elements that are *interpretable*, requiring assigned values; it shows *ephemeral* qualities or elements that are temporal and cannot be captured or defined but are experiential only. Finally, there are *programmable* elements, these are metonymic in nature or sequential and are therefore useful as data input into MMHCI systems.

Table 8. Interpretable, ephemeral and programmable design characteristics emerging from the semiotic analysis.

Design Characteristics	Semiotic	HCI	Yoga	Theatrical Model
Interpretable	Metaphor	Image / Sound	Gesture forms	Performance (expressive gestures)
Ephemeral	Enunciation	User experience	Emotions (engaged by poser)	Emotions (perceived by interactor)
Programmable	Metonymy	Touch Text	Narrative (named gesture progression)	Text

10.0 Conclusion

The problem of reducing the design complexity of expressive gesture in multimodal interaction can be significantly reduced with the application of semiotic analysis. The main advantage is the creation of parity of the human expressive elements with the input and output elements of the technology. The evaluation of *To be or not to be* (not shown here) indicate high levels of interactor completion indicating a successful design in terms of coherency and gesture generation. In particular, the introduction of the term *enunciation*, as a semiotic tool dealing with the temporal nature of expressive gestural interactions, reduces the volatility of an element that is pervasive yet difficult to define.

Three processes emerge from the analysis, namely that there are elements which are *programmable*, that is, they are easily integrated into MMHCI and are usually metonymic in nature; secondly, that there are *interpretable* elements such as designing images and texts and are usually metaphorical in nature and emotions may be structured in these interpretations; thirdly there are *ephemeral* elements which pass and are not readily analysed semiotically.

APPENDIX: 1.0

1a. Interactor Experience: The Design of *To be or not to be*

To be or not be, based on Act 3 sc. 1 ll. 56-61 from Shakespeare play *Hamlet*, was designed to evaluate expressive gesture and emotional experience in human-computer interaction (see reference for online video site [20]). The work was designed for interactive multimodal space where walking gestures performed on an interactive floor pad cause programmed interaction with on-screen film projections. The aim of the work was to generate gestures and emotions in the interactor as a coherent and continuous interface experience.

Interactors walk on a thirty-six square interactive floor pad measuring 3m x 3m connected to a Mac G5 computer which also controls an adjacent 2m x 3m back-projected multimedia screen with sound, which the interactor faces when interacting with the floor pad.

Figure 1a.

Figure 1b.

Figures 1a, 1b. Interactor in two different gesture positions, engaging Step 1 *Text*, the reading of syllabic units and Step 2 *Rehearsal* generating gestures according to game map (upper left hand corner). Step 3 *Performance*, sections of the *Hamlet* film are played back on the same screen once the gesture word puzzle is solved as a correct performance. The entire film will playback as one narrative once all twenty-three word gesture puzzles are solved.

When interactors enter the room the work is in a steady default state displaying a title and brief description. As the interactor walks onto the floor pad, the game cycle is triggered. The interactor is presented with the first screen, a language screen, where large on-screen text of the character Hamlet's monologue appear (see Figures 1a & 1b).

Simultaneously, appears a small interactive map appears on the screen in the upper left-hand corner showing the player's active position on the floor pads. This is represented by interactive green squares allowing navigation. Blue squares flash simultaneously on the map in a pre-programmed pattern; these

are target squares where the user must stand to engage the game. When the user has performed the correct gesture by standing on the blue square position at the right time, that square turns *red* on the map until each blue square of the syllabic syntactic text sequence is extinguished. Achieving this causes a section of film to play. The next word / gesture puzzle to be solved will then appear. A progressive text-map of all the sequences completed appears in the right hand corner. The codes of the map are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Word / gesture game map codes

Blue	Green	Red
<p>target squares established in program to be extinguished; flashing in set sequences</p>	<p>show active walking position of user to aid navigation to find the blue square position</p>	<p>the target has been achieved; user has extinguished a blue square, being in the right place at the right time. Move to next target or film proceeds.</p>

These gesture sequences were designed in a collaborative capacity between artists and programmer. Program design was critical for the reason that the floor pads required a coherent and useable representation by which the interactor could navigate the floor space to complete the game process.

1.b Generating Emotional Response: Interpretable Elements

The emotional response in *To be or not to be* is generated by the film which forms an integral part of the game. The short film is based on lines from Shakespeare's play *Hamlet* Act 3 sc. 1 lines 56-61 [21] a well-known scene where the prince, Hamlet, is suffering from conflicting emotions about his father's murder and his desire for revenge and reflects deeply upon the meaning of life. This is the very same text that generated the syntactic rhythm for the gestures. Actors workshopped the text with the artist / director to develop a semantic, performed interpretation as a film. The interpretation was storyboarded as a narrative film, then shot, edited as one continuous film, then loaded as twenty three segments into the computer as a game designed for the interactive space. As such, the film is an expertly designed message with a definite purpose in communicating the interpreted message as devised by the actors and the director.

The semantic interpretation adopted is tragi-comic, meaning it communicates a sad and also a humorous message in the same work. The film has three groups of characters played by the same three actors alternately. The three groups are *office workers*, *pirates* and *spirits*. The life of office

workers is shown to be colourless and uninteresting; the pirates are fun-loving, playful but temperamental; whilst the spirits watch and react to these two other worlds. The material is designed for teenage audiences who were the focus group for the evaluation study.

These three character dimensions establish the emotional range of the film as: negative, that is sad emotions (office workers); positive, that is happy emotions (pirates); and neutral or other (spirits). The characters associated with these emotions are shown in Figure 2a, 2b, 2c.

Figure 2a. Spirits (neutral)

Figure 2b. Pirates (happy)

Figure 2c. Office workers (sad)

Fig. 2a, 2b, 2c. Scenes from play back sequences in *To be or not be*, activated when the interactor solves a word / gesture sequence (multimedia text removed) showing the three character types and interpreted emotional content as designed by the film director

Table 2 shows a sample storyboard of interactive process showing screen shots and floor plan of the first five word / gesture puzzles in *To be or not to be*. Note gesture position map in left hand corner of screen in Step 1 *Language (Text)*. There are twenty-three puzzle sequences in total. The entire film plays back once all puzzles are solved as the game's goal. Step 1 indicates the presentation of language as a syntactic puzzle of syllabic rhythms to be solved as standing gestures; Step 2 *Syntax (Rehearsal)* shows the standing positions on the floor pad grid that may solve the syntactic puzzle, causing playback of film segments. The interactor engages with an interactive floor pad map of colour coded squares which they must chase to activate the right square in a correct position at a correct time; Step 3 *Semantics (Performance)* shows the interpretive use of language where the same script is used to create a film, guided by directorial intent, to which there is an emotional response by the interactor. Solving each syntactic puzzle reassembles the film, achieving the game goal. For a section of the plan / story-board see Table 2.

Table 2. Sample interactive storyboard showing gestural language, syntax and semantic phases. Gestures are programmable elements as they can be designed as walking gesture sequences; the language of the play – the syntactic rhythm – is used to design the gesture pattern rhythms and to also create the film as interpretation of the same text. The film evokes emotional responses in the audiences.

		G A M E		
C Y C L E	syllabic units	STEP 1 LANGUAGE 		
F U N C T I O N		Gesture/word puzzle based on syllabic units as indicated by flashing left hand square codes on screen. Proceed to Step 2 (solving all twenty-three puzzles, entire assembled film plays back)	User/audience performs gestures on floorpads with the goal of achieving pre-programmed pattern. If achieved, triggers playing of <i>film</i> . Proceed to Step 3	Segmented /film sequence of short Hamlet film. Film generates emotional response. Playing of next text phrase. Return to Step 1
1	to be			
2	or			
3	not to be			
4	that			
5	is			

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